
MEMORANDUM

TO: The Clerk to the Committee
Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs
Parliament of Ghana

FROM: Consortium of Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights (SRHR) Service
Delivery Organisations

- *Planned Parenthood Association of Ghana (PPAG)*
- *Send Ghana*
- *Curious Minds*
- *Youth Harvest Foundation Ghana*
- *JSI Research & Training Institute*

SUBJECT: Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill,
2021

Contact:

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SEPTEMBER 30, 2021
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1.0 INTRODUCTION

The Consortium of Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights (SRHR) service delivery Organisations (*hereinafter referred to as the 'SRHR Consortium'*), made up of the underlisted organisations, which are incorporated in Ghana, wishes to express our gratitude to your Committee for this opportunity to present this Memorandum on the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021 (*hereinafter referred to as 'The Bill'*):

- [Planned Parenthood Association of Ghana \(PPAG\)](#): *The Planned Parenthood Association of Ghana (PPAG) was set up in 1967 to provide family planning services to the people of Ghana. Over the years, its work has expanded to cover a whole range of sexual and reproductive health (SRH) services. Today, in addition to basic family planning support, PPAG provides maternal and child health care, infertility management, and voluntary counselling and testing (VCT) for sexually transmitted infections (STIs) including HIV and AIDS. PPAG delivers services and programmes through 1,356 service points, including 11 permanent clinics, 54 mobile clinics and over 1,000 community-based service points (CBSs). PPAG works to complement the effort of government through the provision of SRHR information and services to marginalised and vulnerable groups including young people.*
- [SEND Ghana](#): *Established in 1998, SEND GHANA vision is a Ghana where people's rights and well-being are guaranteed, and the mission is to promote good governance and the equality of men and women. SEND implements two types of programs: Grassroots Economic Literacy and Policy Advocacy and Livelihood, Food and Nutrition Security. SEND works in over 60 districts with more than 600 grassroot organizations to promote: gender equity and equality in development, livelihood and food security, good governance practices of accountability, transparency, equity and participation, environmental sustainability, strengthening of civil society organizations, peace and conflict management and sexual and reproductive health rights of vulnerable Ghanaians. SEND GHANA is an affiliate of the Social Enterprise Development Foundation of West Africa.*
- [Curious Minds](#): *Curious Minds works to promote the development needs and aspirations of young people in Ghana and across the African continent but with a primary focus on Rights of the Child (RoC) and Adolescent Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights (ASRHR). The Organisation's approach to children and youth development is a rights-based one with full and meaningful participation of young people at all levels of programme/project conceptualisation, planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation.*
- [Youth Harvest Foundation Ghana](#): *Founded in 2002, the Foundation works to empower youth in 4 interconnected programme areas: Education; Adolescents sexual and reproductive health and rights; Entrepreneurial and employable skills; and Agri-business and market system development. YHFG has built up over the years a broad range of programmes supporting and promoting the sexual and reproductive health of young people by providing appropriate education and supporting rights-based advocacy activities.*
- *JSI Research & Training Institute*

On 2 August, The Bill was presented to Parliament for First Reading. The Bill, in its current state, will have grave effects on universal access to and delivery of Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights (SRHR) services, as it seeks to criminalise evidence-based high-impact contributions of SRHR service delivery organisations, whose work has over the years been commended by Government agencies, including the Ghana Health Service, the Ghana AIDS

Commission, National AIDS Control Programme etc. as essential and complementary to their work.

The delivery of comprehensive, high-quality, timely, and targeted SRHR services is critical to eliminating preventable maternal and neonatal mortality and morbidity, including contraceptive services, and to address sexually transmitted infections (STIs) e.g. HIV and cervical cancer, violence against women and girls and ensures services are available and respond to the specific health needs of adolescents and young people.¹ Universal access to sexual and reproductive health is essential not only in achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs) but also in ensuring that this new framework speaks to the needs and aspirations of people around the world and leads to the realisation of their health and human rights.

A Policy Brief from the Research Department of the Parliament of Ghana has highlighted the important place of SRHR as follows²:

International and regional human rights law enshrines states' obligation to provide adequate, accessible and acceptable health care, which includes sexual and reproductive health care. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Art 25) calls for everyone to have access to health care and social services. The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (Art 12) also explicitly outlines the right to the highest attainable standard of health, expanded on in the Covenant's General Comment No. 22 on the right to sexual and reproductive health. The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women also obliges states parties to "take all appropriate measures to eliminate discrimination against women in the field of health care" (Art 12).

In addition to the aforementioned legal instruments, the adoption of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the UN General Assembly in 2015 reinforced states' previously existing obligations to provide human rights-based social protection. Recognizing that social protection includes them, the SDGs specifically call for the integration of sexual and reproductive health and rights into universal health care systems.³

2.0 OBSERVATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

2.1 Undefined Word with far-reaching consequences

¹ WHO, *Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights: A global development, health, and human rights priority* (July 2014)

² This commentary is based on parliamentary policy brief, [Policy Outcome and Challenges of Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights in Ghana: What is the Role of Parliament?](#) Authored by Dr. John Abebrese Boateng, a Senior Development Policy Researcher with the Research Department of the Parliament of Ghana.

³ Target 3.7: By 2030, ensure universal access to sexual and reproductive health-care services, including for family planning, information and education, and the integration of reproductive health into national strategies and programmes

In setting out the Object and Purpose of the Bill, the following words are used, PROPAGANDA, ADVOCACY, PROMOTION, PROTECTION, FUNDING, SUPPORT and RELATED ACTIVITIES. Similarly, Clause 1 of the Bill sets out the application of the Bill and in sub-clause (d) it includes those who are engaged in the *promotion, propagation, advocacy, funding and support* of LGBTQI+. No definitions have been given to these far-reaching words in the Bill.

We are of the considered view that a failure to define these words properly and adequately will have an impact on the work of organisations such as ours which provide life-saving SRHR services and information. As it stands, simply providing medical support to any person or persons the Bill applies to, may attract criminal sanctions. What amounts to promotion, funding, support, advocacy etc. are not spelt out, lending them to very wide and subjective interpretation.

We respectfully recommend that your Committee provides definitions of these words. That way, the full effect of these clauses can be gauged and based on this, we will be able to provide more detailed inputs.

2.2 Interpretations

We find the following provisions in Clause 2, which is the interpretation clause of the Bill, to be problematic.

‘Ally’ is defined to include a person who supports or advocates for the queer community. This definition of ‘ally’ is problematic, as it again begs the question of what amounts to ‘support’ and ‘advocacy’ for the purposes of the Bill. Does anyone providing sexual and reproductive health information and clinical services for LGBTQI+ persons make the service provider an ally?. We provide services on the principle of “No Discrimination, No Return policy” as a universal access to health and do not enquire about Clients sexual orientation.

We further note that the definitions for **‘approved medical help’** and **‘approved medical treatment’** excludes sexual and reproductive health services as provided by SRHR organisations.

It should be noted that the African Commission in its Resolution 275 has urged African governments to prevent acts of violence and discrimination against persons based on their real or perceived gender identity or sexual orientation as this would be inconsistent with the provisions of the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights. Fear of violence and criminalization could limit our provision of services to all manner of persons irrespective of their orientation. This may also promote fear of other people to access SRHR services for fear of being wrongfully identified to ally should they be at a facility for services.

As mentioned by experts from the UN special procedures, the Bill “describes a system of State-sponsored discrimination and violence of such magnitude that its adoption

(...) would appear to constitute an immediate and fundamental breach of State's obligations under international human rights law".⁴

2.3 Criminalisation of the work of SRHR Organisations

Many Clauses in the Bill have criminal sanctions attached to them. For example, medical professionals providing medical services to LGBTI+ people would be at risk of criminal penalties, namely between three to five years imprisonment; Health and Human rights organizations registering, operating or participating in an activity to "support" an organisation working on LGBTI+ people's rights could face up to 10 years of imprisonment.

This would result in the criminalisation of the work of organisations providing SRHR services and information, such as the signatories to this Memorandum and will impede access to essential SRHR services for whole sections of the Ghanaian population.

Clause 5 places an obligation on individuals and institutions to report offences committed under the Act (if passed), and this can be as simple as identifying as LGBTQI+. This has the potential of including member organisations of this SRHR Consortium, which will mean our organisations taking on the added responsibility of reporting the very persons we seek to assist through our public-good service deliveries. This clause is in clear contradiction with the Patient's Charter.

Clause 12 seeks to criminalise the use of media and online platforms to promote and advocate for the activities of LGBTQI+. This clause again begs the question of what amounts to promotion and advocacy. When does education on SRHR issues become advocacy? Will a publication on a website which explores the sexual and reproductive rights of persons, , fall foul of the Bill? Again, the use of the words 'promotes', 'supports' and 'sympathy' in **Clause 12(2)** are very wide and subject to interpretation in the absence of any clear definition. These provisions would seem to be inconsistent with the right to information as guaranteed in the African Charter and the Model Law on Access to Information in Africa adopted by the African Commission, as well as with Article 19 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.

Clause 14(1) criminalises the funding of LGBTQI+ activities. We appeal to your Committee to consider how such practical scenarios play out in the face of the current wording of the Bill: will funding activities for sexual and reproductive health which may have persons who identify as LGBTQI+ attending (with or without the knowledge of the funding organisation) be deemed to be a prohibited activity under the Bill? This certainly opens innocent activity organisers such as members of this SRHR Consortium to criminal liability.

⁴ UN Special Procedures, Analysis of the draft bill presented to the Ghanaian government, 9 August 2021 <https://ghana.un.org/sites/default/files/2021-08/Public%20-%20L%20GHA%2003.08.21%20%283.2021%29.pdf>

Further to the above, **Clauses 15** and **16** deal with disbanding institutions and groups that 'support' LGBTQI+ and prohibits the formation of any such groups. We call on your Committee to consider critically the effect of such a provision on institutions such as those of this SRHR Consortium who have enviable track records of supporting the State in providing the critically needed interventions in Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights to all individuals, including LGBTI.

Our members continue to play the important role at complementing government efforts to ensure unhindered access to health information and services towards securing a healthy population for national development. A key component of our work is to reach underserved people and minority groups, who's health ultimately affects the health of the general population, with essential health information and services including testing and treating sexually transmitted infections and HIV to help reduce the spread.

The Ghanaian authorities have the legal obligation to protect equality and non-discrimination and other fundamental human rights of all people in Ghana. We recommend that Parliament – through your honourable Committee and the august House at plenary - provides clarity in the choice and use of words in the Bill, so that the full extent of the proposed Bill can be understood and further commented on as necessary.

2.4 Impact to access to healthcare for LGBTI people

Furthermore, the bill significantly discourages all manner of persons irrespective of their sexual orientation from accessing the SRHR services and information, and directly criminalises the very SRHR service providers they seek support from. This can further aggravate the access to HIV and STI treatment for all citizens of Ghana, which can escalate to an uncontrollable situation with preventing and treating HIV and other STIs.

3.0 CONCLUSION

This SRHR Consortium is happy to provide additional information, research materials, case studies and to make relevant briefings to your Committee on matters relating to your Consideration of this Bill as we pledge our commitment to supporting the process of ensuring that the Legislative function of our Parliament is performed based on informed positions and evidence.

We know that your Committee and the Parliament of Ghana have always been sensitive about laws it passes and conscious of how draft legislations that infringe the supreme law of the land or have potential to create implementation challenges, play on the reputation of the Parliament of Ghana and its role in Post Legislative Scrutiny.

We trust that the very important work by organisations in the sexual and reproductive health space, and the benefits of these services to the many beneficiaries, will not be lost on your

Committee as you consider the Bill and our Memorandum. We believe that seeking to criminalise institutions and interventions who interface with all manner of persons, as well as hinder the access to healthcare of all persons, leaves much to be desired.

We will appreciate an audience with your Committee to provide any further details to assist in the conduct of this referral to you by the Rt. Hon. Speaker.

4.0 REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

Beyond the many reference documents cited in various parts of this Memorandum, we wish to draw the attention of your Committee to the underlisted for your reference also.

- Universal Declaration on Human Rights
- Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment
- International Covenant on the Economic, Cultural and Social Rights
- International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
- Matrix of the 2017 UPR recommendations made to Ghana
- African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights (Resolution 275)
- African [Banjul] Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights
- Model Law on Access to Information in Africa
- International Conference of Population and Development (ICPD+25) Commitments.